

STUDYING THE THEORETICAL BASIS FOR INCREASING IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY

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Abstract. *Ideological immunity is the ability of individuals to think critically and resist ideologically. Increasing the ideological immunity of young students, that is, strengthening their ideological and psychological protection, is considered as one of the main issues in many universities and educational institutions today. In order to increase the ideological immunity of young people, it is necessary to implement the programs and policies developed by the government and state agencies.*

Keywords: *modern, ideology, profession, information, reinforcement, immunity, personality, ability.*

In the process of modern globalization, the ideological strength of students is of great importance. The rapid spread of information and the influence of different ideologies require resilience for young people. Therefore, methodologies aimed at increasing the ideological immunity of students are an urgent issue. The theoretical foundations of strengthening ideological immunity in students include various ideological influences aimed at providing the necessary cognitive and critical tools in evaluating young people.

Ideological immunity is the ability of individuals to think critically and resist ideologically. It means the ability to resist any information that may threaten their personal development and the well-being of society.

Increasing the ideological immunity of young students, that is, strengthening their ideological and psychological protection, is considered as one of the main issues in many universities and educational institutions today. The current status and methodology of this process consists of several important aspects:

1. Educational programs: focusing on educational programs in Uzbekistan leads to conducting courses and seminars to familiarize students with national values, historical heritage and culture.

2. Youth policy: it is necessary to implement the programs and policies developed by the government and state agencies in order to increase the ideological immunity of the youth. These programs encourage young people to be socially, politically and culturally active.

3. Local and international experiences: it is necessary to study and integrate local and international experiences, analyze the methods used to increase the ideological immunity of students in other countries and adapt them to our context.

4. Innovative approaches: it is possible to increase students' ideological immunity by using modern technologies and methodologies, for example, online courses, interactive seminars and innovative teaching methods.

5. Psychological support and counseling: helping students cope with stress, depression and other psychological conditions, helps to strengthen their ideological immunity.

6. Social activities: increasing students' ideological immunity by involving them in social activities and initiatives, for example, encouraging young people to actively participate in society through social services, volunteer work and other activities.

The methods of increasing ideological immunity are constantly updated in accordance with the requirements of the times, as students face various external and internal threats. It is necessary for educational institutions and state bodies to regularly revise their methodologies and adapt them to the requirements of the times. Currently, in the global education system, methods aimed at developing the ideological competence of students, mechanisms for training competitive specialists and practical pedagogical systems aimed at developing the ideological qualities of future teachers are being integrated into the educational process.

In higher education institutions around the world, special attention is paid to the professional socialization of students, the development of their spiritual, moral and ideological competence, as well as the education of social activity and initiative. Such studies include scientific research on the development of students' ideological immunity. In developed countries, for example, in the United States of America, Russia, Germany, France, China, and Korea, problem-based teaching, modular teaching, blended learning are used to improve students' thinking, early manifestation of their abilities, and increase the effectiveness of mechanisms of spiritual and moral education. learning (blended learning), master classes, webinars, heuristic methods and the use of virtual learning technologies are important.

Therefore, it is necessary to form our views about thoughts, ideas and ideologies. Educating students in the spirit of comprehensively developed, spiritual and moral values, improving a physically and mentally fresh, healthy lifestyle is one of the priority tasks of the state policy. Also, the role of the neighborhood in the development of spiritual and moral qualities such as spirituality, humanitarianism, morality, ideological maturity, patriotism and activity is also important.

The role of the neighborhood in society, family, neighborhood and school are defined as a solid chain of our society. On September 2, 1993, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens” was adopted. Recognition of the neighborhood as an important democratic institution and the basis of civil society in Uzbekistan is also important. Currently, the prestige of the neighborhood institution is increasing, and its legal status is defined for the first time in Article 105 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It also reflects the community and state support of neighborhoods in the process of creating the constitutional and legal foundations of the system of citizens' self-governance bodies.

The civic institution of the neighborhood plays an important role in strengthening social ties and ensuring equality. When young people are influenced by foreign ideologies, this influence is usually not directly felt, but manifests itself through art, economics and social problems. In this process, students are important in forming an attitude based on scientific outlook and national ideas. The method of persuasion teaches students to be intolerant of foreign ideologies.

In the process of realizing the national identity, it is necessary to encourage students to master spiritual values. In this method, it is very important to provide reliable evidence.

The dependence of ideological influence on emotions depends on a number of factors: determination of information precisely, in terms of time and volume; selection of effective evidence to achieve the goal; relevance and effectiveness; figurativeness of speech and other means. However, sometimes the information that is important from the point of view of professors and teachers is not sufficiently presented to students. After class, students listen to teachers' lectures in the conference hall or other places, but often sit without paying attention.

If the most relevant material of the subject is presented in an interesting form, it will help to engage the students. It is very important to maintain interest and attention at a high level for

young people to be influenced ideologically and emotionally. The relevance and novelty of the information provided in the formation of ideological immunity is important. Or discussing current articles, videos, movies and TV shows on ideological and moral issues arouses interest in them. After the film screenings, exchange of impressions between students should be organized, because after a few weeks, new topics can be brought up for discussion. causes.

The opinions of young directors are valuable in studying and solving the problems of modern cinema and youth. One of the well-known filmmakers, answering the question about the “educational importance of cinema”, said: “Its educational role is on the same level as schools and universities. If the words of the educator and the teacher are the law for the child, the child will want to repeat what the main character does in the movie”.

It is important for students not what the hero of the work or group coach is talking about, but also how he is talking. The content of information and the form of its delivery should be carefully prepared for each speech, even when announcing a simple message in the audience, directed to educational goals. In this case, students, in addition to acquiring new knowledge, enter a state of mental passion; otherwise, knowledge does not become belief and immunity.

Perfectly meaningful and methodologically accurate information is not enough to form a person’s active immunity, immunity to propaganda and morals of foreign ideologies. According to the well-known psychologist B.G. Ananiev, the main task of education is not just to provide information, but to develop the student's creative thinking and the ability to independently analyze natural and social phenomena. Therefore, it is necessary to summarize the achievements of ideological education at the world level, create a mechanism of national ideological education and mobilize the people for the purpose of unification.

It is necessary to introduce national ideological education in all organizations and institutions and focus on creating immunity against modern internal and external ideological threats. This creates a psychological and spiritual unity that “we are a nation”. The impact of internal and external threats on every Uzbek will strengthen national unity. A perceived common threat drives a nation to unite.

The principle of word and work unity plays an important role in organizing ideological and educational work with students. It is necessary to confirm their ideas with concrete examples and regularly teach them to apply them in practice. For example, if the consumption of electricity and water is not controlled in an institute or university, if the educational equipment is often broken, if there are leftovers in the canteen, it is useless to encourage students to economize. The environment should nurture the students.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences Professor V.M. Korotov states in his book “Educative Education”: “The method of mutual teaching is presented as a method of ideological and spiritual persuasion. It connects the team, each of its members to ideological and educational work. Because as an active propagator of advanced ideas, the student can enter them deeply and become a person of faith. “Teaching each other is a great help in organizing ideological and educational work outside the auditorium”.

“Beware, people!” it is necessary to keep repeating the call. It is important to preserve our independence, peace, harmony between nations and citizens in society. It is up to each of us to protect our freedom from threats in a complex and sometimes dangerous world.

The debate method is effective in exposing the false values that foreign ideologies attract to young people. Unfortunately, this method is rarely used in practice. In the students’ circle, there is an attempt to turn the atmosphere to a harmful idea in situations where there are different views and opinions. Modern journalistic works dedicated to events from Uzbekistan and foreign

countries can be a source for discussions. Journalists' live impressions of different social strata, including student youth, arouse special interest in them. It can also be useful to use fiction that exposes foreign ideologies in ideological and educational work. One of the ideological threats that poses a serious threat to our society today is the idea of uniting the young independent states into the former Union. Student debates on the works “Fields left by my father” and “Between Two Doors” show that these books are a powerful tool for propaganda against the forces aimed at empowering the Shura system and for forming young people’s conscious critical attitude towards them. possible Live communication helps to eliminate negative perceptions of students’ views, beliefs and feelings.

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